

VEGANISM AS A CONSCIOUS CONSUMPTION TOOL TO COUNTER CLIMATE CHANGE

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1 ABSTRACT

How much does the production and consumption of animal products really contribute to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change? And how would a plant-based diet help mitigate not only climate change, but also other problems such as deforestation, biodiversity loss, soil degradation and desertification, the nitrogen and phosphorus pollution crisis, water and food system security, ocean warming and acidification, overfishing and social justice problems? This review seeks to answer these questions through detailed bibliographical research, using high-quality scientific articles and publications from renowned institutions as references. One of the objectives of this work is to determine whether veganism is an extremely important conscious consumption tool for mitigating or even reversing climate change and other problems it poses. The biggest gap is in the effective communication of this information, so that people are more aware of it and make better food choices. What you put on your plate is of the utmost importance for the future of humanity and the planet.

KEYWORDS: veganism; conscious consumption; climate change; plant-based diet; diet impact

2 INTRODUCTION

Among the most alarming problems humanity faces today is climate change. Various initiatives aim to achieve the Paris Agreement and try to keep global warming at up to 1.5°C or, at most, 2°C by the end of the century. Despite the warnings, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions continue to rise, and in this context, $\frac{1}{3}$ of all global emissions come from 20 companies in the oil and gas industry (REED, 2019), among them Petrobras, a Brazilian state-owned company. For this reason, the main focus is on the energy transition to clean and preferably renewable sources.

However, lurking is a problem whose solution is much more accessible within the context of adopting individual practices of conscious consumption. Concurrently, this approach offers a solution that would significantly reduce GHG emissions, especially methane gas (CH₄), which is 80 times more harmful than carbon dioxide (CO₂) due to its structure that traps more heat in the atmosphere. In this context, CH₄ is responsible for more than 25% of global warming. Reducing its emissions by 45% by 2030 would help meet the Paris Agreement's goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C (UNEP, 2022).

For example, Petrobras' emissions in 2018 alone were 385 million tons of CO₂ equivalent (where CH₄ and other greenhouse gases are accounted for and converted into CO₂) (Climate Accountability Institute, 2020). However, emissions from the 15 largest meat and dairy companies account for a total of 734 million tons of CO₂ equivalent (CO₂ eq.), and in this context, the two largest emitters are JBS and Marfrig, both Brazilian companies whose emissions are, respectively, 540.6 and 201.8 million tons of CO₂ eq. (IATP and The Changing Markets Foundation, 2022). In this regard, it is noteworthy that the amount emitted by JBS is more than twice that of Petrobras, demonstrating the emerging attention that should be given to emissions from animal-based products, in addition to other problems caused by their production and consumption.

In light of this reality, many people are trying to contribute to transforming this scenario by adopting more conscious consumption. In this respect, food has an enormous capacity to significantly and efficiently alter this reality, especially when it comes to reducing or completely excluding animal-based products.

In summary, this study seeks to identify how much a plant-based diet (veganism) can be truly effective as a tool for conscious consumption in combating climate change through an extensive review of the impact of the animal product industry, its environmental impact, and consequently its social implications.

3 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 The Impact of Diet

Globally, $\frac{1}{3}$ of all food produced for human consumption ends up in the trash, amounting to approximately 1.3 billion tons per year (Gustavsson et al., 2011). Furthermore, it is estimated that between 30% and 50% (1.2 to 2 billion tons) of all food produced never reaches the human stomach, mainly due to poor harvesting, storage, and transportation practices, as well as waste from markets and consumers (Aggidis et al., 2013). In Brazil alone, for instance, nearly 130 kilograms of food are wasted annually by an average Brazilian family, with beef and chicken being among the four most wasted foods (Bastos, 2018).

In this regard, in addition to reducing food waste, other practices that can be adopted for more conscious consumption, particularly in terms of food, include a preference for buying locally sourced foods, preferably without pesticides, reducing the consumption of ultra-processed foods, and composting food that cannot be fully utilized. Less widely discussed is the fact that the production and consumption of animal-based products represent a significant portion of GHG emissions, and therefore, their reduction or exclusion deserves special focus.

In this context, when there is a complete exclusion of animal-based products from a diet, the term vegan or plant-based diet can be used. In this sense, veganism can be defined as a philosophy and way of living that seeks to exclude all forms of animal exploitation, as much as possible within society, whether for food or any other purpose, such as hygiene, clothing, and others. Regarding diet, it excludes all animal-derived products, such as meat, dairy, eggs, and honey, for example (The Vegan Society, 2022). It is worth noting that this article explores the term "vegan" only in the context of diet, as other areas would require more complex research.

In terms of GHG emissions, Brazil is the sixth-largest emitter in the world, and the gas responsible for the majority of emissions (51.1%) in the country is methane (CH₄), highlighting a contrast with the main global emitters (Crippa et al., 2023).

According to a recent study, most of Brazil's emissions, about 73.7%, come from food systems, totaling 1.8 billion tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂e). In this figure, the Other Land Use and Forestry sector (which includes deforestation) followed by Agriculture are responsible for 90% of emissions from the food sector. Moreover, beef production alone accounts for 1.4 GtCO₂, or 78% of emissions from food systems (Alencar et al., 2023). Additionally, the food system is responsible for 80% of deforestation, 70% of freshwater use, and is the leading cause of terrestrial biodiversity loss (UNCCD, 2022).

In general, not only beef but also the consumption of other animal-based products directly and indirectly affects climate change, particularly methane emissions; deforestation and biodiversity loss; soil degradation and desertification; the nitrogen and phosphorus

pollution crisis; water security and food system security; ocean warming and acidification; the problem of overfishing; and also social justice issues.

3.2 Climate Change

Regarding climate change, in a scenario where global greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture are projected to increase by 80% by 2050 (Tilman et al., 2014), it is of utmost importance to consider the impact of food choices. It is estimated that the greenhouse gas emissions from individuals who consume meat are twice as high as those of a person following a vegan diet (Scarborough et al., 2014), highlighting the inefficiency of the current food system.

Today, there are significant global efforts toward energy transition, and "the complete elimination of products from ruminants substantially increases the carbon emission space by about 250 GtC," thereby alleviating the excessive pressure on the energy system and reducing mitigation costs by 25% to keep global warming within 2°C (Bryngelsson et al., 2017).

Moreover, the potential for CO₂ removal by converting pastures into native forests is enormous. It is estimated that 265 GtC could be removed in just 19.6 million km², which corresponds to 41% of all land currently used for this purpose. Furthermore, since the industrial era, 240 GtC have been released into the atmosphere, demonstrating that this shift in land use and dietary habits has great potential to mitigate and even reverse climate change (Rao; Jain; Shu, 2015).

In addition to the global recommendation to consume less meat for health reasons, a diet low in meat could already reduce mitigation costs to reach 450 ppm of CO₂ equivalent, meaning the goal of temperature stabilization, by about 50% by 2050 (Stehfest et al., 2009). In light of this, a 50% reduction in the consumption and production of animal-based products by 2050 is necessary to ensure food security and protect the climate and biodiversity (Dawe et al., 2018).

3.2.1 Focus on Methane Emissions

As previously mentioned, methane gas (CH₄) is responsible for over 25% of global warming, and it is 80 times more harmful than carbon dioxide due to its heat-trapping structure in the atmosphere. Additionally, reducing CH₄ emissions by 45% by 2030 would help meet the Paris Agreement's goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C (UNEP, 2022).

In this context, the lifespan of methane, like other greenhouse gases, is shorter than that of carbon dioxide (CO₂), making its reduction a relatively faster way to mitigate the climate crisis (Montzka; Dlugokencky; Butler, 2011).

Considering that the largest source of CH₄ emissions, as previously noted, is livestock farming, it is concluded that reducing methane emissions by 46% could have the same impact as completely eliminating CO₂ emissions (Smith et al., 2013).

3.3 Deforestation and Biodiversity Loss

Land use, particularly deforestation, is a major source of CO₂ emissions. Pastures are the main driver of forest area reduction (71.2%) and the associated carbon loss (71.6%) in South America, followed by commercial croplands (Sy et al., 2015). In this context, livestock production and its derivatives, such as dairy, have a direct impact on deforestation. Consequently, the way people choose to source their protein, whether from animals or plant-based sources, has direct implications on how much forest will continue to be destroyed.

Since the beginning of the century, many scientists have warned that if deforestation continues at its current rate, all of the world's tropical forests will disappear by the end of the century. This would have an extreme impact on the climate, as we can already observe, and would also eliminate most of the animal and plant species on Earth (Urquhart et al., 2001).

Moreover, forests are home to the greatest terrestrial biodiversity, the largest source of non-food biological resources, the largest terrestrial carbon reservoirs, and the main source of land-based precipitation. Keeping them intact, along with forestry and forest-based solutions, can significantly contribute to the development of a carbon-neutral circular bioeconomy (Hetemäki and Seppälä, 2022). In addition, deforestation and biodiversity loss have been identified as key processes that enable the direct transmission of zoonotic infectious diseases, as evidenced by the COVID-19 pandemic (Hetemäki and Seppälä, 2022).

Focusing on biodiversity, it is important to emphasize that its preservation is intrinsically linked to deforestation. Cattle ranching alone is the largest driver of natural habitat loss, and the consumption of animal-based products has an extremely negative impact on the conservation of terrestrial ecosystems and biological diversity (Machovina; Feeley; Ripple, 2015).

Currently, the planet is undergoing its sixth mass extinction, driven by human activity. Additionally, there is a dramatic decline in populations, which will likely have profoundly negative consequences for ecosystem functions and the vital services that sustain civilization. For this reason, this mass extinction is being referred to as "biological annihilation" (Ceballos; Ehrlich; Dirzo, 2017).

In this scenario, livestock farming is the largest contributor. Animal agriculture is the leading factor in biodiversity loss, as it is the primary cause of deforestation, soil degradation, pollution, climate change, overfishing, and coastal zone sedimentation (FAO, 2006).

3.4 Soil Degradation and Desertification

Currently, desertification affects more than 2.7 billion people worldwide. The demand for animal-based products is continually increasing, and with it, the competition for land to raise these animals is also rising. This growing use of land for animal production heightens the risk of degradation in other ecosystems (Scholes, 2018). Consequently, pasturelands are the leading cause of soil degradation, which in turn leads to desertification.

A study by the University of California analyzed the amount of land required for different diets and concluded that a vegan diet requires only 0.13 to 0.14 hectares per person per year, whereas a conventional diet requires 1.08 hectares. In light of this, a plant-based diet reduces land demand by about 87 to 88% (Peters, 2016).

3.5 Nitrogen and Phosphorus Pollution

Today, $\frac{3}{4}$ of global agricultural production is allocated to livestock, meaning it is used to feed animals rather than directly feeding people (Lassaletta et al., 2016). In this process, a significant amount of fertilizers are used, leading to high levels of nitrogen and phosphorus pollution, which compromises water and air quality, the balance of greenhouse gases, ecosystems and biodiversity, as well as soil quality (Sutton et al., 2013).

Some of the impacts include coastal and freshwater dead zones, fish kills, algae blooms, contamination from phosphorus eutrophication and reactive nitrogen, reduced human lifespan due to exposure to air pollutants, ozone layer depletion, loss of species adapted to low nutrient availability, and soil acidification in both natural and agricultural environments, among other issues (Sutton et al., 2013).

Livestock alone consumes 85% of the 14 million tons of nitrogen in crops harvested or imported into the European Union, while the remaining 15% directly feeds humans (Sutton et al., 2011).

If Europe adopted a plant-based diet, obtaining all its protein from plant sources, only 30% of current crops would be needed, resulting in a 70% reduction in nitrogen fertilizer use and its associated pollution (Sutton et al., 2011).

With a shift towards reducing animal-based products, it would be possible to feed the planet with much higher levels of regional self-sufficiency, generating less nitrogen pollution than we currently see (Lassaletta et al., 2016).

3.6 Water and Food System Security

Nitrogen receives special attention as it is one of the planetary boundaries that has already been exceeded (Rockström et al., 2023). However, there are many other compounds contributing to overall pollution, as over 80% of wastewater globally is released into the environment without treatment (UWWAP, 2017).

Agriculture alone is responsible for 70% of global freshwater withdrawals (UWWAP, 2014) and is also a major water polluter due to the use of agricultural fertilizers. This practice discharges vast amounts of agrochemicals, organic matter, medication residues, sediments, and saline drainage into water bodies (Mateo-Sagasta; Zadeh; Turrall, 2017). These water quality issues pose significant risks to public health, food security, biodiversity, and other ecosystem services (UNEP, 2016).

In a vegetarian diet, a person's water footprint is reduced by 36%, roughly 2,300 liters per day (Hoekstra, 2012), and in a vegan diet, this number would decrease even further. To produce 1 kg of animal protein, 100 times more water resources are needed compared to 1 kg of plant-based protein (Pimentel and Pimentel, 1996 apud Pimentel and Pimentel, 2003). In dietary terms, animal production consumes 50% of the cereals produced globally but provides only 13% of the energy (Smith et al., 2013), highlighting its inefficiency in feeding humanity.

Moreover, consuming animal products significantly increases food waste. On average, a consumer wastes 30% of plant and animal products, but the food losses from animal products are much higher: 96% for beef, 90% for pork, 75% for dairy, 50% for poultry, and 40% for eggs (Shepon et al., 2018).

Thus, adopting a diet that excludes animal products is transformative, as it would reduce land use for food production by 76%, with a 19% reduction in arable land; food-related greenhouse gas emissions would decrease by 49%; acidification by 50%; eutrophication by 49%; and freshwater withdrawals, adjusted for scarcity, would decrease by 19% (Poore and Nemecek, 2018).

In this context, fossil fuel-based processes, agriculture, and fishing are critical due to their significant contributions to global warming, freshwater use, land use, and fish population depletion, respectively (Hertwich, 2010).

3.7 The Problem of Overfishing

As a consequence, the production and consumption of animal-based products exacerbates numerous issues, causing enormous negative impacts on ecosystems as a whole. However, many people believe that simply cutting out meat, especially red meat, is enough. This often leads to increased fish consumption, contributing to one of the most pressing problems humanity faces today: the imminent collapse of fish and seafood populations by 2048 (Stokstad, 2006).

Many believe that plastic pollution is the primary cause of this collapse. While plastic pollution is indeed a major problem, overfishing is the real culprit. Approximately 22% of all caught fish are thrown back into the ocean, but they are either dead or near death (Keledjian, 2014). Plastic straws, for instance, account for just 0.03% of all plastic waste in the ocean (Gülsöken, 2018), whereas fishing lines, ropes, and nets make up 52% of the plastic mass in the Great Pacific Garbage Patch (GPGP) (Lebreton, 2018).

Despite this dire situation, global fishing subsidies exceed \$30 billion annually, with 60% of those subsidies directly encouraging unsustainable, destructive, and even illegal fishing practices (Figueres, 2016).

Additionally, consuming land-based animal products also contributes to the collapse, as nearly 25% of the global fish catch is used for fishmeal and fish oil, which are then fed to livestock and aquaculture (Vannuccini, 2004 apud FAO, 2006).

Over the last 50 years, fish and seafood production has quadrupled, and today, more than 50% of this production comes from aquaculture, or fish and seafood farms (Ritchie, 2019). However, this practice is also highly damaging to the environment, as it releases large amounts of waste containing chemicals, such as heavy metals, directly into the water without proper treatment, further harming the ocean (Reed, 2001).

Moreover, the consumption of fish and seafood products leads to several other problems, either directly or indirectly, as will be explained next.

3.8 Ocean Acidification and Warming

In this regard, CO₂ emissions released into the atmosphere directly affect and cause ocean acidification (Orr, J. C. et al., 2005). Over the past 150 years, the surface of the oceans has become 30% more acidic due to human activity (Feely, 2004) and currently absorbs 26% of the CO₂ emitted by anthropogenic actions (Le Quéré, 2016).

Additionally, the climate crisis and the excessive consumption of animal-based products have also caused ocean warming and, consequently, ocean deoxygenation (Wuebbles et al., 2017). This issue is further exacerbated by the significant anthropogenic nutrient input, particularly nitrogen, as previously mentioned (Altieri and Gedan, 2014).

3.9 Social Justice

As can be observed so far, everything is interconnected, and the consumption of animal products, including fish and seafood, is drastically affecting the balance of both land and sea ecosystems. However, this consumption not only impacts the environment but also human relations and social justice.

In addition to significantly contributing to food security issues, the production and consumption of animal products also exacerbate the water crisis and desertification, which strongly contribute to human migration. Furthermore, the populations most affected by the climate crisis are low-income and marginalized communities, further highlighting environmental racism.

Moreover, practices associated with the animal product industry, such as caging and storage of animals, waste collection, and slaughter, have extremely harmful environmental and social externalities, with Black, Indigenous, and impoverished people being the most affected. Therefore, it is evident that the well-being of farm animals is an integral element of environmental justice (Fox, 2023).

The consumption of animal products causes direct and indirect human health problems, resulting in enormous healthcare costs and deaths. It is estimated that a vegan diet could reduce healthcare costs by more than 1 billion US dollars, surpassing the savings from adopting a vegetarian or healthy omnivorous diet (Springmann et al., 2016).

Additionally, the fishing industry is responsible for numerous fatal accidents, making fishing one of the most dangerous professions (Petursdottir; Hannibalsson; Turner, 2001).

Nonetheless, worldwide, agriculture is one of the leading sectors for slave-like labor. In Brazil, agribusiness, particularly cattle ranching, is the largest contributor to this type of modern slavery (OXFAM, 2023).

4 METHODOLOGY

This study utilized bibliographic research to thoroughly examine the correlation between veganism and climate change, as well as other negative impacts caused by the consumption of animal products.

The review was conducted in several stages, beginning with a clear definition of the research problem, which focused on the impact of the production and consumption of animal products and how adopting a plant-based diet could mitigate or even reverse climate change.

To achieve this, various sources were consulted, including scientific articles published in Qualis A1 journals, reports from national and international organizations, documents from social and environmental NGOs, as well as other academic sources and reliable websites. The selection of these sources was prioritized, emphasizing studies and publications by experts in the field and institutions recognized as authorities, such as Oxfam, FAO, UNEP, Observatório do Clima (Climate Observatory), Greenpeace, and NASA.

The data were synthesized and critically analyzed, highlighting patterns and trends in the related literature. The results were examined considering different perspectives on the role of a plant-based diet in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and other issues, such as deforestation and biodiversity loss. Well-founded conclusions were presented, emphasizing the importance of veganism as a viable strategy to mitigate or even reverse climate change.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the research conducted, it is observed that adopting a plant-based, or vegan, diet is a tool for conscious consumption that has a significant positive impact both individually and collectively.

In this regard, a diet free from animal products is not only an essential tool in combating climate change but also a necessary and highly important measure to mitigate: greenhouse gas emissions, particularly methane; deforestation and biodiversity loss; soil degradation and desertification; the nitrogen and phosphorus pollution crisis; water and food system security; ocean warming and acidification; overfishing; and social justice issues.

Despite the substantial scientific effort, some myths are erroneously used as counterarguments against veganism, such as the increased use of land and higher water consumption.

In this sense, as previously mentioned, regarding the myth of increased water resource usage, it is important to highlight that 70% of water withdrawals are allocated to agriculture. A vegetarian diet reduces the water footprint by 36%, which is equivalent to 2,300 liters per day. Moreover, animal protein production uses 100 times more water resources than plant protein production, demonstrating the inconsistency of this fallacy.

As for the myth that if everyone became vegan, more land would be needed to grow food to feed the population, it has been shown that $\frac{3}{4}$ of global agricultural production is allocated to livestock. If everyone became vegan, the existing cultivated land could feed an additional 4 billion people. Furthermore, 50% of the world's grain production is destined for animal production, which only provides 13% of kilocalories, demonstrating the inefficiency of the current food system. Additionally, the consumption of soy and tofu (foods consumed by a large portion of vegans) is criticized, as some people correlate plant-based diets with deforestation and biodiversity loss due to these crops. However, 80% of soy is destined for animal consumption (FAO, 2006), and much of what is consumed by environmentally-conscious individuals comes from agroforestry and organic sources.

Therefore, as previously mentioned, adopting a diet that excludes animal products would reduce land use for food purposes by 76%, with a 19% decrease in arable land; greenhouse gas emissions from food would be reduced by 49%; acidification would decrease by 50%; eutrophication would decline by 49%; and freshwater withdrawals, adjusted for scarcity, would be reduced by 19% (Poore and Nemecek, 2018).

At the same time, it is observed that more and more consumers are seeking vegan options, and the market for these products is experiencing exponential growth, making this dietary change easier and more accessible. For this reason, the plant-based market is estimated to grow to 95.52 billion dollars by 2029 (Meticulous Research, 2022).

This demand primarily stems from people's understanding that this type of diet is beneficial for the environment, their health, and animals, and consequently, it is seen as an effective tool in the pursuit of a more conscious consumption.

However, it is worth noting that it is not only through diet that the current problems faced by humanity will be solved, but it is certainly a good start, as the consumption of animal products is tied to the main issues listed in this article and, therefore, ceasing to consume them is also part of the solution.

6 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Focusing solely on the energy transition is not enough to limit global warming to 2°C, let alone 1.5°C, by the end of the century. It is essential to turn attention to the impact that consuming animal products has and will continue to have on the planet, exacerbating various problems on a colossal scale.

It is evident that a diet free from animal products is an extremely efficient tool for conscious consumption in combating climate change, both individually and collectively. However, given the systemic and structural nature of the food culture, which involves various political and economic interests, it is necessary to strengthen and expand information about plant-based diets to correct the many misconceptions about this type of diet and its real impact and significance, as the biggest gap lies in the prejudice and misinformation among the population.

Therefore, there is an urgent need to disseminate this information more widely so that consumers understand that what they put on their plate is of paramount importance to the future of humanity and the planet. Choosing what to eat is a political act, and it has never been more urgent to make better dietary choices.

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